

Limited passage and functional effects of polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics in a physiologically-relevant *in vitro* human placental co-culture model

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ABSTRACT

The placenta plays a crucial role during pregnancy, yet effective *in vitro* models for placental toxicity testing are limited. In this study, a Transwell co-culture model combining BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells was developed and characterized, and used to study the transport and effects of polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics (PS-MNPs). After 72 h, 8.7 % of 50 nm and 1.2 % of 200 nm of fluorescent (F)PS-MNPs were detected on the basolateral side, while 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were undetectable. Confocal microscopy showed the uptake of 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs by the BeWo b30 and HUVEC cell layer, whereas the 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were only found within the BeWo b30 cell layer. Exposure to PS-MNPs (sizes of 50, 200 and 1000 nm at concentrations of 1–10 µg/mL) did not result in an effect on mitochondrial activity, oxidative stress and gene expression of several functional markers and steroidogenic enzymes. However, LC/MS-MS analysis of the culture media showed a decrease of 17 % in the level of 17- α -estradiol after 72-hour exposure to 1 µg/mL 50 nm PS-MNPs compared to vehicle control. Overall, our data showed limited effects of PS-MNPs on placental cell function *in vitro*, but FPS-MNPs were internalized and detected on the basolateral side in the co-culture. This warrants further studies on effects of MNPs on placental cell function, and particularly steroidogenesis, to assess the potential effects of MNPs during pregnancy.

1. Introduction

Various plastic polymers, such as polyvinylchloride (PVC) and polystyrene (PS), are widely utilized in everyday applications [1]. These plastics can degrade into microplastics (MPs, <5 mm) and nanoplastics (NPs, ≤ 1 µm) [2]. Due to their extensive use and improper waste management, micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) have become pervasive in the environment. Humans are exposed to MNPs through inhalation, ingestion of food and water consumption [3,4,5,6]. Recent studies have detected MNPs in various human matrices, including blood [7], lungs [8], placenta [9], and meconium [10]. The presence of MNPs in placental tissue and meconium raises serious concerns about their potential impact on fetal development and health. However, the extent of

exposure and the mechanisms by which MNPs reach the fetus and their potential effects remain incompletely understood.

Throughout human pregnancy, the placenta undergoes crucial changes to support the growing fetus [11], [12]. Chorionic villi are formed in the first trimester. Each villus is covered with trophoblast cells which enable nutrient and gas exchange while acting as a barrier to harmful substances. The human placenta barrier consists of four key layers: the syncytiotrophoblast, cytotrophoblast, and fetal capillary endothelium, with a basement membrane between the latter two producing structural support. In addition to nutrient and gas exchange, the placenta also plays a key role in steroid hormone formation. Around the 10th week of pregnancy, the placenta becomes the primary source of progesterone and estrogen, gradually takes over the role of the corpus

Abbreviations: E1, Estrone; E3, Estriol; FBS, Fetal bovine serum; HyD, Hybride detector; LY, Lucifer Yellow; MNPs, Micro- and nanoplastics; MPs, Microplastics; NPs, Nanoplastics; PS, Polystyrene; P/s, Penicillin/streptomycin; PVC, Polyvinylchloride; TEER, Transepithelial electrical resistance; UPW, Ultra purified water; 17 α E2, 17 α -estradiol; 17 β E2, 17 β -estradiol.

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luteum [13]. In the second trimester, the placenta becomes more important for the production of steroid hormones, which are essential for fetal development [14]. Additionally, the placenta undergoes increased vascularization, which improves its capacity to supply oxygen and nutrients to the growing fetus. In the third trimester, the placenta is fully developed, reaching maximal capacity in the production of steroid hormones and delivering oxygen and nutrients to the fetus.

Rodents are commonly used in developmental toxicity studies, but their placentas greatly differ from human placentas in both anatomical and functional aspects [15]. For example, the human placental barrier consists of four layers, whereas the rodent placenta has five: the syncytiotrophoblast I and II, cytotrophoblast, basement membrane and the fetal capillary endothelium [16]. To overcome these crucial species-differences, several experimental *in vitro* models have been developed that try to capture the functional aspects of the human placenta. Especially more complex models with multiple cell types have the potential to mimic the human anatomical architecture of placental tissue and foster cell-cell interactions, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of placental responses. While many *in vitro* co-culture models have effectively explored placental barrier function, other critical roles of the placenta, such as metabolism and steroidogenesis, remain comparatively under-studied [17], [18]. For example, one co-culture model has examined the transport of PS-MNPs, showing that 1.3 % of the initial concentration of 40 nm PS-MNP was detected on the basolateral side, while no transfer of 70 nm particles was observed [17]. However, this study did not address potential changes in biological functions.

The aim of this study is to study the effects of nano-sized PS-MNPs on placental function in a novel *in vitro* co-culture model using BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells that closely mimics the *in vivo* structural arrangement. In addition to establishing this model, several biological processes i.e. perturbations in mitochondrial activity, ATP levels, transport, uptake, oxidative stress, steroidogenesis, and gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes and placental markers were evaluated after exposure to PS-MNPs of various sizes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell culture conditions

BeWo b30 cells were purchased from Addexbio (San Diego, CA, USA). BeWo b30 cells (passage numbers used in experiments: 4–12) were cultured in DMEM/F-12, GlutaMAX™ growth medium (31331–028), supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS, 10270–106) and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin (p/s, 15140–122). The assay medium used was DMEM/F-12 (1:1) 1x (11039–021) supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % p/s. All materials above were derived from Gibco (Breda, The Netherlands). HUVEC were purchased from Lonza (Morrisville, NC, USA). HUVEC (passage numbers used in experiments: 4–7) were cultured in endothelial cell growth medium (CC-3124, Lonza) and, for the assay, phenol red free medium (CC-3129, Lonza) was used with supplements (CC-4133, Lonza). Both cell lines were sub-cultured using 0.05 % trypsin-EDTA solution (15400–054, Gibco), cultivated in a humidified incubator (37 °C, 5 % CO₂).

2.2. Formation of transwell cultures

The formation of BeWo b30 and HUVEC monoculture are described in A.1. The BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture was established on 12-wells Corning polycarbonate Transwell inserts (3402, Corning) with a pore size of 3 µm. The Transwell inserts were coated basolaterally with 0.2 mL 50 µg/mL human placental coating IV (9007–34–5, Sigma). Next, 0.5 mL cell suspension (2.0*10⁵ BeWo b30 cells/mL) was applied to the apical side on day 1 and medium was refreshed on day 3. Transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements were performed on days 3 and 5. On day 5, the inserts containing BeWo b30 cells were placed

upside down into a petri dish and 0.2 mL of the HUVEC cell suspension (5.0*10⁵ cells/mL) was added on the basolateral side of the inserts. After 2 h, the inserts were placed back into the 12-well plate. The apical side was filled with 0.5 mL of BeWo b30 medium, and the basolateral side was filled with 1.5 mL of HUVEC medium. TEER measurements and medium refreshment were performed on day 8. Day 9 was chosen as starting point for exposure. To evaluate the suitability of this model for prolonged exposures (72 h), the model was exposed to assay medium used for exposures. An overview of this method is presented in Fig. 1. Barrier integrity of the Transwell monocultures (BeWo b30 and HUVEC) and co-culture (BeWo b30/HUVEC) was assessed by TEER measurements, Lucifer yellow (LY) transport, immunocytochemistry and histological analysis. More detailed information about the methods are described in A2. The effects of PS-MNPs on mitochondrial activity, particle translocation, cellular uptake, oxidative stress, steroidogenesis and gene expression were performed between day 9 and 12, as described below in paragraph 2.3.

2.3. Polystyrene micro- and nanoplastic exposure

2.3.1. Preparation of exposure medium

All MNPs particles were purchased from Polysciences. More detailed information about the supplier and sample preparation is provided in A.3. The co-culture was apically exposed for 72 h to 50, 200 or 1000 nm of PS-MNPs on day 9, in concentrations of 1 or 10 µg/mL (1000 times dilution from stock, with a final concentration of 0.1 % ultra purified water(UPW)) in BeWo b30 assay medium (0.5 mL). The growth medium in the basolateral chamber was replaced by HUVEC assay medium (1.5 mL) The concentrations used in this study, were chosen based on the levels of polystyrene found in human blood [7].

2.3.2. Mitochondrial activity monocultures

A MTT assay was performed to determine mitochondrial activity in the individual cell lines BeWo b30 and HUVEC (2D cultures) after exposure to PS-MNPs and fluorescent PS-MNPs (FPS-MNPs). The method is described in more detail in A.4.

2.3.3. Mitochondrial activity in Transwell co-culture

2.3.3.1. *Resazurin assay.* Resazurin (62658–13–8, Sigma-Aldrich) was diluted in PBS (final resazurin concentration of 22 µM) and added to the apical (0.5 mL) and basolateral (1.5 mL) side on day 12 of the co-culture. The plates were placed in the incubator for 90 min. A 0.1 mL sample was taken from the apical and basolateral side and transferred into a black 96-well plate (Greiner, 655900). The samples were measured in the Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (excitation 530, emission 590). Data analysis was performed with excel and Graphpad (version 10.1). All exposures were normalized to the vehicle-treated control (=100 %) within each experiment. After this, the means of each experiment was averaged and SD was calculated from this average.

2.3.3.2. *ATP measurements.* On day 9 of the co-culture, the cells were exposed for 72 h to the different PS-MNPs as described earlier. An ATP (34369–07–8, Sigma-Aldrich) calibration curve ranging from 0.2 µM to 100 µM was prepared using 25 µL of each ATP concentration mixed with 75 µL lysis buffer (CellTiter-Glo®, G755B, Promega) in white 96-well plate (Greiner, 655904). To determine ATP levels in the samples, medium from the apical and basolateral side was removed by vacuuming. Lysis buffer was diluted 1:1 in BeWo b30 assay medium, and 300 µL was added to the apical side. The cells were removed from the apical and basolateral side of the membrane with this diluted lysis buffer and then transferred to an Eppendorf Tube. 50 µL of cell solution was mixed with 50 µL pure lysis buffer and transferred to the white 96-well plate. Subsequently, the plate was analyzed using the Biotek Cytation 5 (Luminescence). Fold changes in ATP levels in comparison to the vehicle-

Fig. 1. Experimental procedure for establishing the co-culture of BeWo b30 and HUVEC. On day 1, the basolateral side of the Transwell inserts was coated with human placental coating IV, followed by the seeding of BeWo b30 cells on the apical side. After 5 days, the inserts were inverted in a petri dish, and HUVEC cells were seeded on the basolateral side of the insert. After 2 h, the insert was placed back in the 12-well plate. Exposure to MNPs took place from day 9 to day 12. Created with Biorender®.

treated control (=1) were calculated in MS-Excel.

2.3.4. Translocation of FPS-MNPs in the co-culture

Three calibration curves were prepared using a dilution series for each size PS-MNPs in a black 96-well plate (Greiner, 655900) ranging from 10 µg/mL to 0 µg/mL. The fluorescence values were measured using a Biotek Cytation 5 (excitation: 485 nm, emission: 528), with the 0 µg/mL sample (0.1 % UPW) serving as the background. Background fluorescence was subtracted from the other calibration points, and the corrected values were used to generate a calibration curve in Graphpad Prism version 10.1. On day 9 of the co-culture, 5, 24, 48, and 72 h after adding the FPS-MNPs, 100 µL samples were taken from the basolateral side and measured in the black well plate using the Biotek Cytation 5, with 100 µL HUVEC assay medium freshly added after each sampling. For each time point, the samples of the vehicle-treated control cells were taken to determine background fluorescence, which was averaged and subtracted from the corresponding exposure sample values. The corrected values were then used to calculate the interpolated x-values, representing the amount of fluorescent particles transferred from the apical to the basolateral side. Additional calculations were performed to account for dilution effects from the repeated addition of fresh medium.

2.3.5. Cellular uptake

The cells were seeded on the Transwell membrane as described in A.1. The procedures for cytoplasmic and nuclear staining and imaging are described in detail in A.5. Imaging was performed on a Leica SP8 confocal microscope, equipped with a 405 laser, and a tuneable white light laser. All images were made with a magnification of 63x and 2x

zoom.

2.3.6. ROS measurements

A 1 mM solution of DCFA-DA (D6883, Sigma-Aldrich) was prepared in BeWo b30 assay medium. On day 9 of the co-culture, the medium on the apical side was removed, and 250 µL of the probe solution was added to the apical side. The cells were incubated for 30 min (37 °C, 5 % CO₂). After this incubation period, the probe solution was removed, and the cells were washed with 500 µL PBS. The cells were exposed to 1 or 10 µg/mL PS-MNPs in various sizes, with the addition of two positive controls: 100 µM Menadione (58-27-5, Sigma-Aldrich) and 0.3 % H₂O₂ (107298, Supelco). The plates were measured using the Biotek Cytation 5 (excitation: 485 nm, emission: 528 nm) at time points 24, 48, and 72 h.

2.3.7. Steroid hormone analysis

Measurements of the steroid hormone profile were carried out as previously described [19], [20], [21]. Details about the method are given in A.6. In short, 100 µL aliquots of the media on the apical and basolateral side were used for steroid hormone analysis. This was done for the monocultured Transwell BeWo b30 (day 12) and HUVEC (day 8) after 72 h exposure to assay medium containing PS-MNPs. For the co-culture, steroid hormone analysis was performed after 72 h exposure to PS-MNPs in concentration 1 or 10 µg/mL. Medium was stored in the -80 °C until analysis. Solid phase extraction was performed to isolate the steroid hormones (see A.6) and the extracts were measured on an ExionLC system (Sciex, Framingham, MA, U.S.). Cortisol was excluded from analysis due to high levels present in HUVEC medium. Peak

integration was performed by SCIEX OS and the data was transferred to MS-Excel. Absolute pg levels of steroid hormones were calculated to pg/mL. The average of the triplicate, for each steroid hormone, was taken within each experiment. The average of each individual experiment was used to calculate average hormone levels in three independent experiments. Further analysis was performed with Graphpad (version 10.1). Hormones that were measured but were below the LOD were 17 α -OH-progesterone, 11-deoxycortico and 11-deoxycortisol. Other hormones that were not detected at all were: 5 α -androstenedione, DHT, aldosterone, testosterone, androstenedione, 5 α -THDOC, etioch-3 α -one, DHEA, 5 α -androsterone, 5 α -androstendiol and 17-OH-DHP.

2.3.8. Gene expression

For RNA extraction, the chloroform method was used for both the monocultures and the co-culture (for more details see A.7.1). RNA samples were diluted to 100 ng/ μ L. The co-cultures were exposed for 72 h to 10 μ g/mL PS-MNPs in different size or the positive control for induction of steroidogenesis (10 μ M Forskolin, 66575–29–9, Sigma-Aldrich). cDNA synthesis was performed using the cDNA-Biorad mycycler™ thermal cycler (see A.7.2). Expression was analyzed in BeWo b30 and HUVEC models for selected genes (primer sequences are given in Table A.7.3). A qPCR was conducted using the Biorad CFX96™ real-time system (for more details see A.7.4) with the following protocol: an initial 5-minute step at 95°C, followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C and 45 s at 60°C. The melt curve analysis involved a 5-second step at 60°C, with the temperature increasing by 0.5°C increments until reaching 95°C. For data analysis, fluorescence drift correction and baseline subtraction were applied, with the graph converted to a log scale and the baseline threshold set at 600 relative fluorescent units (RFUs). Genes with a Ct value greater than 33 were considered undetected. Using the Biorad CFX Maestro software, a gene expression study was conducted with settings configured for normalized expression ($\Delta\Delta$ Cq) and data relative to zero. GAPDH, HRT1, and TBP were used as reference genes. Changes in gene expression were calculated relative to vehicle-treated control (0.1 % UPW) using MS-excel. Means and standard deviations from three

independent experiments were calculated.

2.4. Statistical analysis

All statistical analysis were performed using Graphpad prism 10.0. Data is presented as a mean \pm SD unless otherwise stated. Prior to analysis, data was tested for normality using Shapiro-Wilk test. For comparisons between the vehicle-treated control and positive controls, unpaired two-tailed Student's t-tests (95 % confidence interval) was applied. For comparisons of the vehicle-treated control to exposures, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All experiments were independently repeated at least three times in triplicate.

3. Results

3.1. Optimization of mono-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells and co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC cells

Before establishing the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture, the barrier integrity of each monoculture grown on Transwell inserts was evaluated. The monoculture of BeWo b30 showed an increase in TEER over time, reaching the threshold of approximately 350 Ω /cm² and demonstrating LY permeability below 1 % by day 9 (Fig. 2A), indicating the formation of a tight monolayer suitable for further experiments. In contrast, the monoculture of HUVEC showed an increase in TEER from day 3 to day 8, with LY permeability decreasing from 3.9 % to 1.6 % (Fig. 2B). Despite this trend, the defined tight barrier criterion was not achieved, even with extended culture duration.

In the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture, barrier integrity was assessed by monitoring TEER and LY permeability on days 3, 5, 8–12 (Fig. 2C). By day 9, TEER values exceeded 350 Ω /cm² and LY permeability was below 1 %. At day 9, the culture media was replaced with assay medium. This did not affect the TEER and/or LY passage until day 12, indicating a successful maintenance of barrier integrity.

Fig. 2. Barrier integrity of the monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells and co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC using trans epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) and lucifer yellow (LY). The TEER (in Ω /cm² on left Y-axis) and transfer of LY (% of total LY added apically on right Y-axis) was measured for the monocultured (A) BeWo b30 and (B) HUVEC and for the (C) co-culture BeWo b30/HUVEC over several days. The dots and bars represent the average of three individual experiments in triplicate. The dotted line represents the arbitrary limit of 1 % transfer of LY. For graphs A & B: the bars represent the average of two individual experiments and for graph C: the bars represent the average of three individual experiments.

To confirm the formation of monolayers in the mono- and co-cultures, immunocytochemistry was performed using ZO-1 and Hoechst staining (Fig. A.8 for monocultures). Both markers confirmed uniform cell coverage across the membrane of the insert and the formation of tight junctions. On day 9, microscopic examination revealed the presence of tight junctions in both BeWo b30 and HUVEC layers of the co-culture (Fig. 3A-B). On day 12, tight junctions remained visible (Fig. 3C-D), confirming that the barrier was maintained after 72 h of culture. Histological analysis confirmed that BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells were at the apical and basolateral side, respectively (Fig. 3E-F). Additional Hoechst staining confirmed that BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells were present at the apical and basolateral side of the membrane of the insert, respectively (Fig. 3F).

3.2. Characterization of mono-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells and co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC cells

To characterize the monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC and the co-culture, gene expression analysis and steroid hormone profiles were measured. qPCR was used to identify the presence of cell type specific markers in monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC (see A.9). *InhA-1*, *InhA-2* and *TNF α* were only detected in BeWo b30 cells, while *NOX4* and *p-selectin* were specific for HUVEC cells. These markers were used to assess if it was possible to isolate RNA from the individual cell lines within the co-culture model. However, clean isolation of RNA from the single cell-lines in the co-culture was not feasible. To investigate the differences in steroid hormone profiles between monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells, steroid hormone levels were measured in the medium from the apical and basolateral sides of the monocultures and co-culture (Fig. 4). In media from monocultured HUVEC cells, only the two steroid hormones corticosterone and cortisone were identified, whereas in media from monocultured BeWo b30 cells, six steroid hormones were detected, namely pregnenolone, progesterone, cortisone, estrone (E1), 17 α -estradiol (17 α -E2), and 17 β -estradiol (17 β -E2). In all cultures, the concentrations of hormones appear higher on the apical side of the culture, except for E1 in the monocultured BeWo b30. All ratios between the hormones are described in Table A.10. In the co-culture, E1 levels were below the LOD for the apical and basolateral side. In monocultured BeWo b30 cells, pregnenolone levels in the apical

side were higher than in the co-culture, being 11,6208 pg/mL and 40,557 pg/mL, respectively. Cortisone levels were lower at the apical side of monocultured BeWo b30 (285 pg/mL) compared to the apical side of the co-culture (16,469 pg/mL). In contrast, 17 α E2 and 17 β E2 levels were lower in the co-culture compared to the BeWo b30 monoculture on the apical and basolateral side.

3.3. Polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics exposure

3.3.1. Mitochondrial activity in mono- and co-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells

Before assessing the effects of polystyrene particles in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture model, an MTT assay was performed on mono-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells after exposure to a concentration range of 0.01–100 μ g/mL (F)PS-MNPs in different sizes (see Fig. A.4.2). Exposure to 100 μ g/mL of 1000 nm FPS-MNPs resulted in an increased (24 %) mitochondrial activity in HUVEC cells. None of the other exposures affected mitochondrial activity in BeWo b30 or HUVEC cells. Next, a resazurin assay was performed to evaluate the effect of PS-MNPs on mitochondrial activity in co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC cells using media from the apical and basolateral side after a 72 h exposure. The positive control (10 % DMSO) caused a statistically significant reduction in mitochondrial activity in the co-culture (Fig. 5A-B). None of the tested sizes or concentrations PS-MNPs had any significant effect on mitochondrial activity in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture.

3.3.2. ATP measurements

ATP levels are an indicator of cell viability, particularly of mitochondrial activity, as mitochondria are primarily responsible for ATP production. ATP levels in the co-culture were assessed using the Cell Titer Glo assay after exposure to PS-MNPs for 72 h. Mitochondrial activity thresholds were defined as a 0.8 and 1.2-fold change relative to the vehicle-treated control cells. None of the PS-MNP exposures affected ATP levels, whereas the positive control (10 % DMSO) showed a statistically significant decrease in ATP of 92 % compared to the vehicle-treated co-culture (Fig. 6).

3.3.3. Translocation of MNPs across the different cultures

To determine the translocation of PS-MNPs across the cell layers,

Fig. 3. Immunohistochemistry and histology on the co-culture inserts. Representative images show the tight junction (ZO-1, red) and nuclei (Hoechst, blue) for (A and C) BeWo b30 cells and (B and D) HUVEC cells on day 9 (A and B) and day 12 (C and D). Pictures from histological analysis (E and F) show a side view of a 5 μ m cut insert. AS = apical side, BS = basolateral side, scale bar = 100 μ m. Shown pictures are representative examples of duplicate experiments with similar results.

Fig. 4. Steroid hormone profiles in the Transwell mono-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells, and in co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC cells. The colors in the heatmap represents the concentration of the steroid hormone present with the lightest being the least level of hormones and the darkest being the highest level of hormones. The values represent the level of that hormone per model (in pg/mL). This data shows the average of two individual experiment performed in triplicate for mono-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC and three individual experiments in triplicate for the co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC. B = monocultured BeWo b30, H = monocultured HUVEC, B/H = co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC.

Fig. 5. Resazurin assay in the co-culture. Mitochondrial activity was measured in the (A) apical and (B) basolateral after exposure to PS-MNPs for 72 h. The arbitrary thresholds were set at 80 % and 120 % (dotted lines). The bars represents the average \pm SD from three individual experiments in triplicate. Statistical significance was determined with one-way ANOVA or student's *t*-test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$).

Fig. 6. ATP level in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture upon exposure to PS-MNPs. ATP levels were measured inside the cells using the CellTiterGlo assay after exposure to the different sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs. The threshold was set at 0.8 and 1.2 fold-change. The bars represent the average \pm SD of three individual experiments in triplicates. Statistical analysis was performed with one-way ANOVA or student's *t*-test (**** $p < 0.0001$).

monocultured and co-cultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells, were exposed to 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ 50, 200 or 1000 nm FPS-MNPs on the apical side. Transport of the FPS-MNPs was monitored at 5, 24, 48 and 72 h. All tested sizes of FPS-MNPs were detected at the basolateral side in the BeWo b30 and HUVEC mono-cultures (Fig. 7A-B). In the BeWo b30 monoculture, 50, 200 and 1000 nm FPS-MNPs particles were detected on the basolateral side after 5 h (3.7 %, 3.5 %, 0.98 % respectively) and the maximum amount of particles in the basolateral chamber was reached after 48 h (18.2 %, 5.5 % and 2.4 % respectively) (Fig. 7A). In the HUVEC monoculture, higher levels of FPS-MNPs were detected for all particle sizes compared to monocultured BeWo b30, with a maximum after 72 h (17.8 % for 50 nm, 8.4 % for 200 nm, and 9.2 % for 1000 nm) (Fig. 7B). In the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture, 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs were detected in the basolateral side after 5 h (2.42 % and 0.33 % respectively, displayed in Fig. 7C), with the amount increasing over time. After 72 h, 8.7 % of the 50 nm and 1.2 % of the 200 nm particles were detected in the basolateral side. In contrast, the 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were not detected in the basolateral side after 72 h (Fig. 7C).

Fig. 7. Translocation of FPS-MNPs through the monocultured BeWo b30, monocultured HUVEC and co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC cell layers. Translocation studies were performed from day 9 until day 12 post seeding for (A) monocultured BeWo b30, (B) monocultured HUVEC and the (C) co-culture. Percentages of FPS-MNPs translocation were corrected for volume differences and are expressed in comparison with the vehicle control treated cells (0.1 % UPW). Data points represent the average and SD of three individual experiments in triplicate.

3.3.4. Uptake of FPS-MNPs into the cellular compartment of the co-culture

To further assess the location of the particles, the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture was exposed to 1 µg/mL FPS-MNPs on the apical side and microscopically assessed after 72 h. The 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs were detected in the BeWo b30 and the HUVEC cell layers (Fig. 8C-F), while

1000 nm FPS-MNPs were only detected in the BeWo b30 layer (Fig. 8G-H). 3D analysis showed that the FPS-MNPs were internalized by the cells (Fig. 9), with 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs internalized by the BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells (Fig. 9A-F), while 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were only internalized by BeWo b30 cells (Fig. 9G-H).

Fig. 8. Representative images of the location of FPS-MNPs in the cellular compartments of the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture after 72-hour exposure. The BeWo b30 (upper panels, A, C, E, G) and the HUVEC (lower panels, B, D, F, H) layer is shown for the vehicle control (A, B), 50 nm FPS-MNPs (C, D), 200 nm FPS-MNPs (E, F) and 1000 nm FPS-MNPs (G, H). The cell membrane and cytoplasm are stained with red (CellMask), nuclei are blue (Hoechst), and the FPS-MNPs are green (some are indicated with arrows). The scale bar indicates 50 µm.

Fig. 9. Representative 3D reconstructions of the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture after exposure to FPS-MNPs. Z-stack imaging was used to generate 3D reconstructions of the cellular layers (A, D and G). The arrows indicate the location of a FPS particle. For each particle size, a white box highlights a region of interest, which is further magnified in the corresponding images below (50 nm: BC, 200 nm: EF, 1000 nm H). In the images, red represents the cell membrane and cytoplasm, blue indicates the nuclei, and green denotes the FPS-MNPs. Scale bar indicates 10 μm for A, D and G, 5 μm for F, 2 μm for B, E and H, and 1 μm for C.

3.3.5. ROS measurements

ROS production was measured after 24, 48 and 72 h of exposure to PS-MNPs using the DCFA-DA assay. The positive controls, H₂O₂ (Fig. A.11) and 100 μM Menadione (Fig. 10), statistically significantly increased ROS levels at all time points, with H₂O₂ inducing fold changes of 15.2, 8.6, and 7.9, at t = 24 h, 48 h and 72 h, respectively. In contrast, none of the PS-MNPs exposures caused a statistically significant change in ROS production (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Oxidative stress measured in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture. A DCFA-DA assay was used to determine the production of ROS after exposure to 50, 200 and 1000 nm at concentrations of 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ PS-MNPs. Menadione (100 μM) was used as positive control. Bars represent means \pm SD of three individual experiments in triplicate. ROS in vehicle-treated control treated cells was set as 1. Statistical analysis was performed with Students *t*-test for the positive control and one-way ANOVA for the concentrations PS-MNPs (* $p < 0.05$).

3.3.6. Steroid hormone profile

To assess potential effects on steroid hormone levels, BeWo b30/HUVEC co-cultures were exposed to various sizes and concentrations of PS-MNPs for 72 h. Forskolin (10 μM) was used as a positive control for induction of steroidogenesis. The media were analyzed for 23 steroid hormones using LC-MS/MS, but only six steroid hormones were detected in vehicle-treated control cells. These steroid hormones included pregnenolone (40,557 pg/mL), progesterone (27,795 pg/mL), corticosterone (1924 pg/mL), cortisone (16,469 pg/mL), 17 α E2 (722 pg/mL) and 17 β E2 (103 pg/mL) on the apical side and pregnenolone (10,148 pg/mL), progesterone (15,154 pg/mL), corticosterone (1875 pg/mL), cortisone (14,925 pg/mL), 17 α E2 (141 pg/mL) and 17 β E2 (19 pg/mL) on the basolateral side of the co-culture. The positive control forskolin statistically significantly increased all steroid hormone levels measured at the apical side, except 17 β E2 (Fig. 11D). Forskolin induced the largest effect on pregnenolone levels, resulting in an increase from 40,557 pg/mL to 88,357 pg/mL in the apical side and from 10,148 pg/mL to 27,585 pg/mL in the basolateral side. In contrast, corticosterone levels were lower in the apical side upon forskolin exposure, with 1924 pg/mL (vehicle control) to 875 pg/mL (forskolin exposed) in the apical side. The only statistically significant effect upon PS-MNPs exposure was a 17% decrease in 17 α -E2 levels in the media at the apical side, being 722 pg/mL in vehicle control and 604 pg/mL (0.83 \pm 0.08-fold) following exposure to 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of 50 nm PS-MNPs (Fig. 11A-C).

3.3.7. Gene expression

The impact of PS-MNPs on gene expression related to steroidogenic enzymes and placental function was assessed using qPCR. Forskolin was used as positive control and resulted in statistically significantly increased gene expression of CYP11A1 (2.1-fold), CYP17 (11.5-fold), Leptin (6.4-fold), and PGF (1.9-fold) compared to vehicle-treated

Fig. 11. The effect of PS-MNPs on steroid hormone levels in the apical and basolateral compartments of BeWo b30/HUVEC co-cultures. Heatmaps showing fold-changes, ranging from 0.5 (purple) to 3 (orange), in steroid hormone levels in the apical or basolateral side media of the co-culture upon exposure to 1 or 10 μ g/mL PS-MNPs with sizes (A) 50 nm, (B) 200 nm and (C) 1000 nm. (D) Forskolin (10 μ M) was also included as a positive control for induction of steroidogenesis. The values in each cell represent the hormone level measured in pg/mL. The fold-changes and hormone levels in pg/mL were measured in three individual experiments in triplicate. Statistical significance for exposure to PS-MNPs was calculated with one-way ANOVA, Dunnett's multiple comparison test (* $p < 0.05$). Statistical significance for exposure to Forskolin was calculated with a student's t -test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$).

control cultures. Exposure to PS-MNPs had no effect on the gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes (Fig. 12A-E), nor on the gene expression of Flt-2, Leptin, PGF and PLAC8 (Fig. 12F-I).

4. Discussion

The unique features of the human placenta makes it a challenging organ to investigate in toxicological studies. While experimental, rodent *in vivo* models may capture the complexities of the placenta, they present issues such as limited representativeness for the human situation and ethical dilemmas. There are some *in vitro* models that account for the complex interaction between different placental cell types. However, only a few of these models capture the multiple cell layers that compounds need to cross from the maternal compartment to the fetal circulation in the human placenta i.e. the syncytiotrophoblast, cytotrophoblast, basement membrane and the fetal capillary endothelium [17], [22]. Importantly, none of these models fully capture the hemodynamic environment of the placenta, which plays a critical role in regulating nutrient and compound transfer. In this study, we aimed to develop an *in vitro* model to better mimic the human placental barrier function by using a co-culture of BeWo b30 cells, as model for cytotrophoblasts, and HUVEC cells, as model for fetal endothelial cells. Moreover, the human placental coating may surrogate for the placental basal membrane and provide an additional physical layer thereby, better mimicking the human placental barrier *in vivo*.

Our study showed that 50, 200 and 1000 nm FPS-MNPs could pass the monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC cell layers, while in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture only 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs were detected in the basolateral side. Notably, the translocation of 200 nm FPS-MNPs was minimal, with only 1.2 % crossing the co-culture barrier after 72 h. Additionally, the maximum amount of 50 nm FPS-MNPs detected

in the basolateral side was higher in the BeWo b30 and HUVEC mono-cultures than in the co-culture (18.2 % and 17.8 % versus 8.7 %, respectively). In a similar model to ours, using BeWo b30 and HPEC-A2 cells, it was shown that 1.3 % of 40 nm FPS-MNPs were detected at the basolateral side after 24 h, while 70 nm particles were not detected [17]. In addition, we showed that 50 and 200 nm FPS-MNPs were present inside the BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells of the co-culture, while 1000 nm FPS-MNPs were only observed in the BeWo b30 layer of the co-culture. Several studies have reported the detection of substantially larger MNPs (ranging from 5000 to 50,000 nm) within placental tissues [9], [10]. However, our findings are in line with placental perfusion studies using term human placentas showing that FPS-MNPs of ≤ 500 nm can pass the placental barrier to the fetal side [23], [24]. This suggests that the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture model offers a morphologically relevant representation of the human placental barrier when it comes to passage of MNPs. It is important to note that term placentas differ structurally and functionally from earlier trimesters, and extrapolations to earlier stages of pregnancy should be made with caution. Nevertheless, our model seems to represent second and third trimester placental function, at least in term of barrier function, and together with other studies strongly indicate that small, nano-sized PS-MNPs are able to enter placental cells and ultimately the fetal environment.

Especially during pregnancy, disruption of mitochondrial activity may result in adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preeclampsia [25], [26], miscarriage and compromised fetal development [27]. Mitochondria are essential for cellular energy production and regulation of metabolic processes [28]. Oxidative stress, often assessed by measuring ROS levels, is not only a key indicator of cellular damage but is also closely linked to mitochondrial function, as mitochondria are the primary source of ROS in cells [29]. In our study, the effects of PS-MNPs on

Fig. 12. The effect of PS-MNPs on gene expression in BeWo b30/HUVEC co-cultures. The co-culture was exposed apically for 72 h to 1 or 10 μg/mL PS-MNPs in different sizes (50, 200 and 1000 nm). The vehicle treated control cells were exposed to 0.1 % UPW and forskolin (10 μM) was used as positive control for induction of steroidogenic gene expression. Gene expression was normalized to three housekeeping genes (GAPDH, TBP, HPRT1). Bars represent the average \pm SD fold change of three individual experiments (N = 3). Statistical significance was determined by a student's *t*-test (**p* < 0.05) for the positive control and one-way ANOVA for the exposures. Abbreviations: 17β1-HSD, 17beta1-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase; 3β-HSD, 3beta-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase; CYP, cytochrome P450; Flt-2, fms like tyrosine kinase-2; PGF, placental growth factor; PLAC8, placenta associated 8.

mitochondrial function were assessed in the BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture using four different readouts namely MTT, resazurin conversion, ATP and ROS production. Our data indicated no statistically significant effect on mitochondrial function after 72 h of exposure to 1 and 10 μg/mL of PS-MNPs of various sizes. To our knowledge, this is the first study investigating the effect of PS-MNPs in a placental co-culture using a Transwell format. In mono-cultured BeWo b30 cells in flat-bottom 96-well plates, exposure to high concentrations of PS-MNPs (1000 μg/mL of 50 and 100 nm) resulted in reduced mitochondrial activity, assessed by an MTT assay [30]. Another study with monocultured BeWo b30 cells in flat-bottom 96-well plates showed no effect of PS-MNPs on ATP levels (0.1–100 μg/mL for 50, 200 and 1000 nm) [31]. Exposure to 500 nm, but not 100 nm, PS-MNPs has been linked to decreased mitochondrial activity in HUVEC cells at concentrations of 50 and 100 μg/mL [32]. Other studies using HUVEC cells also demonstrated that exposure to similar sizes (ranging from 20 to 10,000 nm) PS-MNPs at concentrations of \leq 100 μg/mL did not result in elevated ROS levels [32,33,34]. Taken together, our study indicates minimal effects of PS-MNPs on mitochondrial activity in our more complex co-culture compared to conventional monocultures. This may partly be explained by the fact that we studied effects in a co-culture in a Transwell format that allows cellular polarization. Cellular uptake of MNPs in polarized epithelial cells may differ from conventional 2D cultures, for

example through polarized vesicle transport [35,36] or differential expression of membrane transporters at the apical and basolateral side of the cells [37,38]. Generally, cellular uptake of MNPs is considered to take place via endocytosis, phagocytosis and passive diffusion [39,40], although the mechanism of MNPs uptake in cells is not completely understood. In our study, we assessed ZO-1 expression, which is a marker for tight junctions and formation of a tight mono-layer. It should be further investigated whether the differences observed between our study and others may be attributed to differential expression of membrane transporters in placental cells. Moreover, different effects between our studies and others may be a result of different types of MNPs used between the studies; as toxicological research on MNPs is an emerging though rapidly growing field, the lack of standardized methods and reference material seriously hampers comparison between studies. We used lower concentrations and smaller sizes of PS-MNPs than most other studies, which may be below the threshold needed to induce significant effects on mitochondrial activity. The tested concentrations in our study are comparable to the concentration PS detected in human blood (4.8 μg/mL) [7]. This concentration was determined using pyrolysis GC-MS, where particles \geq 700 nm were filtered out before determining polymer concentrations. Given the higher uptake and distribution of nano-sized particles, i.e. particles < 1000 nm, which suggests that actual MNP levels in human blood may even be higher. However, to the

best of our knowledge, so far no studies have been performed that adequately assess nano-sized particle numbers in human samples. Clearly, more encompassing methods are highly needed to determine MNP exposure, thereby assessing polymer types, particle sizes, shape and number, which would greatly enhance the interpretation of experimental data and human exposure data for human risk assessment.

The placenta plays a crucial role in steroidogenesis during pregnancy and disruption has been implicated in adverse pregnancy outcomes [41], [42]. In our study, steroid hormone levels detected in the co-culture media were lower than those in the monocultures, suggesting the presence of paracrine signaling between BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells. This interaction may better replicate the hormonal balance maintained in the placenta during pregnancy. In humans, maternal serum pregnenolone concentrations range from 330 pg/mL to 4760 pg/mL during pregnancy between gestational weeks 7–29 [43], while pregnenolone levels in cord blood reach 17,340 pg/mL at birth [44]. Progesterone levels during pregnancy vary from 100,000 pg/mL to 200,000 pg/mL in term placental tissue [45], and up to 478,000 pg/mL in cord blood [46]. Furthermore, maternal serum levels of 17 β -E2 during the third trimester are approximately 13,850 pg/mL [47], whereas cord blood levels are reported at 2900 pg/mL [46]. The ratios of steroid hormones (detailed in A.6) indicate that the ratios in BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture better resemble human physiological ratios during pregnancy. For example, the pregnenolone ratio (apical/basolateral) was 20.7 for the monocultured BeWo b30, 4.0 for the co-culture and 0.3 (4760/17,340) in humans. Similarly, the ratio for progesterone was 6.4 for the monocultured BeWo b30, 1.8 for the co-culture and 0.4 in humans (200,000/478,000). The ratio for 17 β E2 was 4.2 for monocultured BeWo b30 and 5.4 for the co-culture compared to 4.8 in humans (4.8). Based on these ratios, it seems that the steroidogenesis in the co-culture is comparable to steroidogenesis in human placenta.

In our BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture, a statistically significant 17 % reduction in 17 α -E2 levels was observed following a 72 h exposure to 1 μ g/mL of 50 nm PS-MNPs. There were no changes in gene expression of steroidogenic enzymes to corroborate this. 17 α -E2, despite having a lower affinity for estrogen receptors compared to 17 β -E2 [48], plays a crucial role in maintaining uterine quiescence during pregnancy [49], thereby preventing premature labor. Clearly, this warrants further investigation on the potential effects of MNPs on placental

steroidogenesis, and 17 α -E2 in particular. Here, it would be imperative to consider the complex interplay in the fetoplacental unit with respect to hormone contributions from maternal adrenal glands and fetal steroidogenesis [50,51].

This study describes the successful development of an *in vitro* placental co-culture model that mimics the human placenta in terms of its structural layers and steroidogenesis. Using this BeWo b30/HUVEC co-culture model, we showed that nano-sized polystyrene particles were internalized and transported across the placental cell layer, similar to what is observed in *ex vivo* human placental perfusion models. Additionally, a decrease in 17 α -E2 levels after PS-MNPs exposure was observed, indicating that further investigation into effects on placental steroidogenesis may be warranted.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sandra M. Nijmeijer: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Jeske van Boxel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **van Duursen Majorie B. M.:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sebastian Rupp:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Investigation. **Manuel T. Heinzelmann:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

A.1 Transwell monoculture formation

On day 1, the basolateral side of a 12-well Transwell inserts (3402, Corning), with pore size 3 μ m, was coated with 200 μ L 50 μ g/mL human placental coating IV (9007–34–5, Sigma). The way the cells were monoculture

A.1.1 Monocultured BeWo b30

A suspension of BeWo b30 cells (2.0×10^5 cells/mL) was prepared, and 0.5 mL of this suspension was added to the apical side. 1.5 mL of BeWo b30 growth medium was added to the basolateral side. The plate was then placed in the incubator (day 1). On day 3, 5, 8, 9–12, the transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) and lucifer yellow (LY) transport was measured. Medium was refreshed on day 3, 5, and 8. On day 9, the monoculture was exposed to BeWo b30 assay medium for 72 h.

A.1.2 Monocultured HUVEC

A HUVEC cell suspension was prepared (5×10^5 cells/mL) and 0.2 mL of this cell suspension was added to the basolateral side of the inserts. The inserts were then incubated for 2 h in the incubator. Afterwards, the inserts were placed back in the 12 well plate and HUVEC growth medium was added to both sides (1.5 mL basolateral, 0.5 mL apical). On day 3–8 TEER and LY transport was measured. Medium was refreshed on day 3, and 4. On day 5, the monoculture was exposed to HUVEC assay medium for 72 h.

A.2 Barrier integrity

A.2.1 TEER and Lucifer yellow

Barrier integrity of the Transwell monocultures (BeWo and HUVEC) and co-culture (BeWo/HUVEC) were determined by measuring TEER (EVOM²,

world precision instruments, 182033) with an electrode (STX2, world precision instruments, M08C) and LY (L453, ThermoFisher) transport. LY was dissolved in HUVEC assay medium (1 mg/mL). In a black 96-well plate (Greiner, 655900), a calibration curve of LY (ranging from 100 – 0 %), and this curve was measured using a plate reader (Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (Biotek, Vermont, USA)). Subsequently, in the apical side 0.5 mL of 1 mg/mL LY solution was added and 0.1 mL from the basolateral side was collected and measured as background. The plate containing LY was then placed in the incubator for 1 h. After incubation, 0.1 mL was removed from the basolateral side and measured using the same plate reader. The fluorescence of LY was corrected for the volume difference and with interpolated x-values on the calibration curve the percentage of passage over the barrier was determined. Data analysis was performed with excel or Graphpad (Version 10.1). TEER measurements were corrected for the surface (1.12–1 cm).

A.2.2 Staining procedure on inserts

The membranes were placed in a 24 well plate (Greiner, 662160), were fixed with 0.35 mL 4 % PFA in PBS and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. After this, the inserts were washed three times with PBS. Thereafter, 0.1 % triton in PBS was added to the inserts and incubated for 20 min, followed by another three washes with PBS. A mixture of 10 % lamb serum, 0.1 % TWEEN 20 in PBS was added (0.35 mL) and incubated for 10 min at 200 rpm on the shaker. The inserts were washed three times with 0.1 % TWEEN 20 in PBS. The inserts were incubated with the ZO-1 primary antibody (Cell Signaling Technology Cat# 13663, RRID:AB_2798287), 1:200 in PBS (10 % lamb serum, 0.1 % TWEEN 20)) overnight at room temperature. After the incubation, the inserts were washed 3 times with PBS (0.1 % TWEEN 20). The secondary antibody alexa-594-rabbit (Invitrogen, Goat Anti-Rabbit, A11012, 1:400 in PBS (10 % serum, 0.1 % TWEEN)) was incubated for 1 h at room temperature (200 rpm on shaker). The inserts were washed 3 times with normal PBS. 50 µL Hoechst (Invitrogen H3569, 10 mg/mL) was added into 0.5 mL medium of the apical side. This was incubated for 10 min at room temperature, whereafter solutions were removed from the wells. The membranes were removed from the well plates and placed on a microscopic slide (VWR, 631–0108) and were covered with a cover glass (VWR, ECN631–1574). Images were acquired on fluorescent microscope (Leica DMI6000, room temperature, 40x magnification) using three different channels; brightfield, DAPI (excitation 360 nm, emission 460 nm), GFP (excitation 480 nm, emission 505 nm) and Texas Red (excitation 600 nm, emission 615 nm). An overlay was prepared with the LASX software.

A.2.3: Detailed information for histological analysis

The cells for the co-culture were seeded as described previously. After 12 days the membrane was cut out of the insert, as described above, and fixed in 4 % PFA for 15 min and washed once with PBS. The inserts were placed in 70 % ethanol and after this the inserts were cut in half. Samples were embedded in 1 % agarose (in demi water) and placed into embedding cassettes (VWR, 720–2177)[52]. These were placed into the tissue processor and a standard 38 h dehydration process was performed (HistoCore PEARL; Leica), see table A.2.1.

Table A.2.1
The procedure of the dehydration process (HistoCore PEARL; Leica)

Step	Reagent	Duration (hours)
1	80 % ethanol	1
2-3	90 % ethanol	1
4-5	95 % ethanol	1
6-7	100 % ethanol	1
8-10	Xylene	2 – 4-12
11-12	Paraffin	8 – 8 (60 °C)

After the dehydration process, the agarose blocks were placed into metal embedding molds, embedded in paraffin and the paraffin blocks were placed on an ice cold plate (HistoCore Arcadia H) to cool down the sample. After this, sections were taken at 5 µm thickness using a rotary microtome (Microm HM 355S; Thermo Fisher Scientific) using 80 mm disposable microtome blades (MX35, ultralow 34° profile; Thermo Fisher Scientific). The samples were placed on a microscopic slide. Staining with Hematoxylin and Eosin was performed with an automatic stainer (ST5010 Autostainer XL; Leica), see table A.2.2.

Table A.2.2
The staining procedure with the ST5010 Autostainer XL; Leica

Step	Reagent	Time (min)
1-2	Xylene	2
3-4	100 % ethanol	2
5	95 % ethanol	2
6	Tap water	2
7	Hematoxylin	3
8	Tap water	1
9	Differentiator (tap water + 1 drop acetic acid)	1
10	Tap water	1
11	Bluing (tap water)	1
12	Tap water	1
13	95 % ethanol	1
14	Eosin	0.75
15	95 % ethanol	1
16-17	100 % ethanol	1
18-19	Xylene	2

After this, a drop of mounting medium (Sigma, 25608–33–7) was placed on the sample and covered with a cover slip. Images were acquired with a Leica microscope (Mateo TL RUO, 11526238) with the brightfield channel with a magnification of 40x.

A.3 Polystyrene particles

Table A.3
Additional information about the purchased PS-MNPs

Particle	Supplier	Name product	Cat. No.
FPS_50 nm	Polysciences	Fluoresbrite ® YG Microspheres	17149-10
FPS_200 nm	Polysciences	Fluoresbrite ® YG Microspheres	17151-10
FPS_1000 nm	Polysciences	Fluoresbrite ® YG Microspheres	17154-10
PS_50 nm	Polysciences	Polybead ® Microspheres	08691-10
PS_200 nm	Polysciences	Polybead ® Microspheres	07304-15
PS_1000 nm	Polysciences	Polybead ® Microspheres	07310-15

Characterization of PS particles

The PS-MNPs were obtained from Polysciences (Table A.3). According to the manufacturer’s specifications, the particles had a diameter of 50, 200 or 1000 nm. The particles were supplied in an aqueous suspension, diluted to 10, and 1 mg/mL in filtered UPW and stored according to the supplier’s instructions. Prior to exposure, the particles were diluted directly in cell culture medium. No visible aggregation or precipitation was observed under light microscopy throughout the 72-hour exposure period. As expected for PS under static conditions, most of the PS particles sedimented onto the cell monolayer over time. Uptake images (Figs. 8 and 9) further show that the PS MNPs particles did not agglomerate during the exposure period.

A.4: MTT in mono-culture BeWo b30 and HUVEC

A.4.1. Method

BeWo b30 (2.87×10^5 cells/mL) and HUVEC (2.86×10^5 cells/mL) were seeded in a 48 well plate (Greiner). BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells were exposed to different concentrations (F)PS-MNPs, ranging from 0.01 to 100 µg/mL for 72 h. After the incubation period, exposure medium was removed and stored for the LDH leakage assay. 250 µL MTT solution (1 mg/mL in assay medium) was added per well. After 1 h incubation, the MTT solution was removed and 250 µL isopropanol was added and placed on the shaker until cells are lysed. Absorbance was measured at 595 nm in the Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (Biotek, Vermont, USA). Data analysis was performed with excel and Graphpad (version 10.1). The control was set at 100 % and all exposures were compared with the control. Statistical analysis was performed with one-way anova in Graphpad.

A.4.2 Results

An MTT was performed to assess the impact of PS-MNPs and FPS-MNPs on the BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells in monoculture. Mitochondrial activity was considered affected if it fell below 80 % or exceeded 120 %. None of the exposures affected the mitochondrial activity of BeWo b30 (Fig. A.1.2 A and B). However, exposure to 1 µg/mL of 200 nm PS-MNPs resulted in a statistically significant decrease in mitochondrial activity (Fig. A.1.2 C and D), although it did not fall below the thresholds (84.4 %). A similar result was observed for exposure to 0.01 µg/mL of 1000 nm FPS-MNPs (Figure A.1.2D), where the viability was just below the threshold (119.2 %). Nevertheless, exposure to 100 µg/mL of 1000 nm FPS-MNPs resulted in a statistical significant increase mitochondrial activity (123.8 %).

Figure A.4.2. Impact of (F)PS-MNPs on mitochondrial activity of HUVEC. The MTT assay results reveal the effects of diverse concentrations and sizes of (F)PS-MNPs on cellular viability. Notably, only exposure to 100 µg/mL of 1000 nm FPS-MNPs surpassed the critical threshold (>120 %). Each bar in the graph represents the average ± SD from three independent experiments in triplicate, with the control set at 100 %. The dotted line signifies the thresholds for affected mitochondrial activity (80 % and 120 %). Statistical significance is denoted as * for p < 0.05

A.5: More details about staining and imaging fluorescent images after PS exposure

A.5.1 Staining

On day 9, the apical side was exposed to 1 µg/mL FPS-MNPs with sizes 50, 200 or 1000 nm or to a negative control (0.1 % UPW)(0.5 mL). These exposures were prepared in BeWo b30 assay medium. The growth HUVEC medium in the basolateral side was replaced with 1.5 mL of HUVEC assay medium. After 72 h, the medium from both sides were removed, the membranes were excised with a surgical blade (Swann Morton, BS 2982) and then precisely cut to separate the two sides (apical and basolateral), allowing for subsequent analysis of each size independently. The membranes were placed in a 24 well plate (Greiner, 662160) and washed three times with PBS. After this, the cells were incubated for 5 min at 37 °C with 350 µL 1000x diluted CellMask (Invitrogen, C10045) in PBS. The membranes were washed three times with PBS and after that fixed with 4 % PFA for 15 min at room temperature. The membranes were washed once with PBS and then incubated with 350 µL Hoechst (Invitrogen H3569, 10 mg/mL) in PBS for 5 min. The membranes were removed from the well plates and placed between two cover glasses (VWR, ECN631–1574) with mowiol mounting gel [53].

A.5.2 Imaging

Hoechst was excited with the 405 laser, and emission was detected using a photomultiplier tube in the range of 411–450. FPS-MNPs were excited using the 405 laser with emission detection between 496 and 548 nm using a hybrid detector (HyD). CellMask orange was excited with the white light laser set to 553 nm and detected using a HyD set to 558–676 nm. Z-Stacks of 40 µm with a step size of 160 nm (starting with the HUVEC layer closest to objective) were recorded with compensation of laser power (Hoechst 4–35 % and cell stain 0.1–8) to account for sample thickness. Laser power for the FPS-MNPs was adjusted for the BeWo b30 cell layer without compensation (1000 nm FPS-MNPs: 0.5 %, 200 nm FPS-MNPs: 6 %, 50 nm FPS-MNPs: 6 %, Control: 6 %), to ensure detection of FPS-MNPs on the HUVEC cell layer. Images were deconvolved using standard parameters in batch mode (deconTemplateBatch.hgsd) in SVI Huygens software (version 24.04). Images were converted to 8-bit in imageJ [54]. Images were imported into LASX software to produce final 3D images.

A.6: Extraction steroid hormones and measurements with LC-MS/MS

All the steroid hormones used for analysis are described in table A.6. In brief, the extraction of steroid hormones from 100 µL exposure medium was carried out through solid-phase extraction using 30 mg Plexa cartridges (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, California). For this process, a SCIEX Triple Quad 6500 + System, a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer with an electrospray ionization source, was employed in both positive and negative modes (SCIEX, Framingham, MA, USA). The instrument settings included a curtain gas set at 35 psi, temperature at 600 °C, ion source gas 1 at 70 psi, ion source gas 2 at 50 psi, and ion spray voltage ranging from 5500 to –4500 V. Steroid hormones were separated using a Kinetex® C18 LC Column (2.6 µm, 100 × 2.1 mm) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA) maintained at 40 °C and operated on an ExionLC system (SCIEX, Framingham, MA, U.S.) with a binary pump and autosampler. For the underivatized LCMS/MS method, the settings included A: MeOH and B: 0.2 mM NH₄F in MilliQ, with a changing ratio and a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min (Table A.6.2). Each run lasted 22 min, monitoring analytes through multiple reaction monitoring. Steroid hormones such as 5α-THDOC, etioch-3α-one, 5α-androsterone, 5α-androstenediol, DHT, and aldosterone were not detected in the medium. The extracted were then dansylated to measure estrogen levels. The dansylation was performed by evaporate the extracts and dissolve them in a carbonate buffer and 1 mg/mL dansyl chloride (605–65–2, Sigma-Aldrich) in acetone. These were then measured with the same settings as the underivatized method, but with small modifications in elution gradient to better separate the estradiol isomers (table A.6.2). With the derivatized LCMS/MS method, estrone (E1), 17-β-estradiol (17βE2), and estriol (E3) were measured. Dansylation of the samples involved adding 1 mg/mL dansyl chloride (Sigma-Aldrich) and carbonate buffer to each sample. Data analysis included normalizing the data per experiment to the control (defined as 1). The impact of PS-MNPs exposure on hormone levels in H295R cells was expressed as fold changes compared to the control. Average fold changes per experiment, along with their standard deviation, were calculated. To determine statistical significance, a one-way ANOVA Dunnett's multiple comparisons test was applied, comparing the mean of each column with the mean of a control column.

Table A.6.1

All steroid hormones used for LCMSMS analysis including their concentration range in pg used for the calibration curve

Internal standard	CAS no.	Supplier	Concentration range (pg) calibration curve
DHT	521–18–6	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	8–9345
17OH-pregnenolone	1164–98–3	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	6–16930
Pregnenolone	145–13–1	Sanbio (Uden, the Netherlands)	8–15087
17OH-progesterone	68–96–2	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	9–15264
Testosterone	58–22–0	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	10–12919
Androstenedione	63–05–8	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	10–8319
Corticosterone	50–22–6	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	8–16046
11-deoxycorticosterone	64–85–7	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	6–13424
11-deoxycortisol	152–58–9	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	117–14911
Cortisol	50–23–7	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
Progesterone	57–83–0	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	8–10824
Cortisone	53–06–5	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	10–15113
DHEA	53–43–0	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	18–7645
Androstanedione	846–46–8	Euroisotop (Saint-Aubin, France)	5–16106
Androstenedione 13C3	63–05–8	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
DHT D3	79037–34–6	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
Cortisol D4	73565–87–4	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
Corticosterone D4	50–22–6	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
17OH-prog 13C3	68–96–2	Eurisotop (Saint-Aubin, France)	-
Cortisone D8	53–06–5	Eurisotop (Saint-Aubin, France)	-
Androsterone D4	53–41–8	Eurisotop (Saint-Aubin, France)	-
DHEA D6	52–43–0	IsoSciences (Ambler, PA, USA)	-
Testosterone 13C3	58–22–0	IsoSciences (Ambler, PA, USA)	-

(continued on next page)

Table A.6.1 (continued)

Internal standard	CAS no.	Supplier	Concentration range (pg) calibration curve
Androstenedione 13C3	846-46-8	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
Progesterone 13C3	327048-87-3	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
Pregnenolone 13C2,2H2	1852-38-6	Eurisotop (Saint-Aubin, France)	-
11-deoxycortisol D5	1258063-56-7	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
E1	53-16-7	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	1-41
17bE2	50-28-2	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	0.2-52
E3	50-27-1	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	0.8-48
17aE2	57-91-0	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	0.3-48
17bE2 13C3	79037-37-9	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
E1 13C3	1255639-56-5	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-
E3 13C3	1241684-29-6	Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands)	-

Table A.6.2

Solvent gradient profiles in LC-MS/MS

Gradient underivatized			Gradient dansylated		
Time (min)	Flow (mL/min)	MeOH (%)	Time (min)	Flow (mL/min)	MeOH (%)
0	0.6	20	0	0.6	20
0.5	0.6	45	3.5	0.6	55
4.5	0.6	55	5.5	0.6	55
5.5	0.6	55	9.3	0.6	81
12	0.6	99	15.1	0.6	95
16.5	0.6	99	18	0.6	95
16.6	0.6	20	18.01	0.6	20
18.5	0.6	20	20	0.6	20

A.7: More details about qPCR

A.7.1: Chloroform extraction

BeWo b30 or/and HUVEC cells were seeded on the membrane of inserts of a Transwell® system as described previously. Firstly, the cells were washed with cold PBS, whereafter 500 µL trizol (Molecular research center, inc. iTaq™, Cat no. TR-118) was added to remove the BeWo b30 cells from the membrane. For the HUVEC cells, 200 of the 500 µL was used to remove the cells. The samples were collected in Eppendorf tubes and freezed at -80 °C until use. Each tube received 100 µL of chloroform (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 67-66-3) at ice-cold temperature, followed by vortexing for 20 s. The resulting mixture underwent centrifugation at 12000 g for 15 min at 4 °C (consistent throughout the procedure). Subsequently, 200 µL of the upper layer was transferred to a new Eppendorf tube. To this tube, 250 µL of ice-cold isopropanol (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 67-63-0) was added and vortexed. The tubes were incubated for 1 h at 4 °C, after which the supernatant was removed. Then, 750 µL of ice-cold ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, CAS no. 64-17-5) was added, followed by vortexing. The tubes underwent centrifugation, and the supernatant was once again removed. The pellet was washed with 750 µL of ice-cold ethanol, and the supernatant was removed. The pellet was then dried for 10 min at room temperature. Subsequently, the pellet was resuspended in 15 µL of cold sterile water and kept on ice. RNA levels were measured using the Biotek Cytation 5 plate reader (Biotek, Vermont, USA) at 230 nm. Subsequently, the samples were standardized to a concentration of 100 ng/µL in Eppendorf tubes by adding the appropriate amount of DEPC (Invitrogen, Part. No. 46-2224).

A.7.2: cDNA preparation

Ten microliters of normalized RNA were transferred to PCR tubes, followed by the addition of 10 µL of mastermix per sample (composed of 2 µL 10x RT buffer, 0.8 µL 25x DNTP mix, 2 µL 10x random primers, 1 µL REF transcriptase, and 4.2 µL DEPC) in each PCR tube. These tubes underwent cDNA preparation in the cDNA-Biorad mycycler™ thermal cycler. The protocol initiated with a 10-minute incubation at 25 °C, followed by 120 min at 37 °C, 5 min at 85 °C, and a cooldown to 4 °C. The cDNA was then diluted tenfold by adding 180 µL DEPC, followed by gentle vortexing of the tubes.

A.7.3: primer sequences

Table A.7.3

The sequences of the primers used in this study

Gene	Forward primer	Reverse primer
3B-HSD	CCACACCGCTGTATCATTGATGTCT	TAGGAGITGGGCCCGCTACCT
CD34	TGATTGCACTGGTCACCTCG	TAAGGGTCTTCGCCAGCC
CYP11A1	TGCATCTTCAGTCGTGTGCCAA	AGGTGACCACTGAGAACCATTCA
CYP17	TGCTTATTAAGAAGGCAAGGACTT	TGTTGGACGCGATGTCTAGAGT
CYP19	GCACATCCTCAATACCAAGTCC	TCCAGAGATCCAGACTCGCA
EDNT1	CTACTTCTGCCACCTGGACATC	TCACGGTCTGTTCCTTTGTGG
Flt1	TTGGGACTGTGGGAAGAAACA	TGTCCGCAGTAAAAATCCAAGT
GAPDH	TCGACAGTCAGCCGCATCT	AGTTAAAAGCAGCCCTGGTGA
HSD17B1	CCTAAGCAAGTCCGAGAAGGAA	AAGGTAGTACAGGCCACGA

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Table A.7.3 (continued)

Gene	Forward primer	Reverse primer
IL6	CCACCGGAACGAAAGAGAA	TCTCCTGGGGTATTGTGGA
InhA-1	ATGTCTCCAAGCCATCCTTTT	GGCCGGAACATGTATCTGAA
InhA-2	GTCTCCAAGCCATCCTTTTC	TGGCCGGAACATGTATCTGAA
Leptin	CACCAGGATCAATGACATTTTACA	TGAAGTCCAAACCGGTGACT
NOS2	TCCCAGTCAGAGTCACCAT	TCCATGCAGACAACCTTGGG
NOS3	GACCCACTGGTGTCTCTTG	CCCGAACACACAGAACCTGA
NOX1	CTGTTGCCTAGAAGGGCTCC	ACAGGCCAATGTTGACCCAA
NOX4	CACCAGATGTTGGGGCTAGG	TGATCCTCGGAGGTAAGCCA
PECAM1	ACGTGCAGTACACGGAAGT	GGAGCCTTCCGTCTTAGAGT
PGF	AATGTCACCATGCAGCTCCTA	TGGCAGTCTGTGGGTCTCTG
PLAC8	TCCTGCTCGGAACCTTGTIT	GTGCCACAGACAGACTCC
PPAR α	TGGCCGATCGCCGTG	TGGCTTCTTCAAATCTGGTGT
SOD2	GGCTACGTGAACAACCTGA	TTCCAGCAACTCCCCTTTGG
SPINT1	CGGATGTCAGGGTAGAGAGGA	GTTGGATGCGAGGCAGTAGT
TNF α	GCTGCACITTTGGAGTGATCG	CTTGCTACTCGGGTTTCGAG
VEGFA	CAACAAATGTGAATGCAGACCAA	GCTCCAGGGCATTAGACAGC

A.7.4: qPCR protocol

2.5 μ L of cDNA was added to each well of the PCR plate, along with 7.5 μ L of mastermix 2 per sample (comprising 5 μ L SYBR green from Bio-rad Laboratories, Veenendaal, Ref. No. 1725124, and 2.5 μ L of 2.5 μ M primer with an end concentration of 0.25 μ M). A plastic layer was applied to the PCR plate, which underwent centrifugation for 1 min at 2000 rpm. The PCR plate was then positioned in the Biorad CFX96TM real-time system, following a protocol of 5 min at 95 $^{\circ}$ C, followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95 $^{\circ}$ C and 45 s at 60 $^{\circ}$ C.

A.8: Staining of the monolayers of BeWo b30 and HUVEC

To confirm the establishment of well-formed monolayers on day 9 for BeWo b30 and day 5 for HUVEC, immunocytochemistry using ZO-1 and Hoechst was conducted. The Hoechst staining showed that the BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells were well spread over the whole inserts (Fig. A.8 A,D). Interestingly, noticeable differences in tight junctions were observed between the BeWo b30 (Fig. A.8B) and HUVEC (Fig. A.8E) monolayers. Histological analysis showed that there is a monolayer of BeWo b30 (Fig. A.8 C), but that the HUVEC monolayer did not showed a similar monolayer (Fig. A.8F).

Figure A.8. Staining of the Transwell monolayers of BeWo b30 or HUVEC. The BeWo b30 monolayer was stained for Hoechst and ZO-1 (A-B) and eosin and hematoxyline (C). The same was done for the HUVEC monolayer (D-F). The BeWo b30 cells are smaller and the tight junctions are more present in comparison with the HUVEC cells. The HUVEC cells are more extended cells, where the ZO-1 staining is not that present, but still visible

A.9: Gene expression in monocultured BeWo b30/HUVEC

A panel of genes was examined using qPCR to identify presence in BeWo b30 or HUVEC. The results (Fig. A.9) revealed that most tested genes were expressed in BeWo b30, only CYP17, IL-6, NOX4 and p-selectin was not expressed. In HUVEC, CYP17, IL-6, InhA-1, InhA-2 and TNF α was not expressed.

Figure A.9. Presence of genes in the Transwell mono-culture of BeWo b30 and HUVEC cells. The green colors represents that a gene is expressed in BeWo b30 or HUVEC, while a brown color represents it is not expressed. These results are based on two individual experiments

A.10: Steroid hormone ratios monocultured BeWo b30 and HUVEC and the co-cultured BeWo b30/HUVEC

Table A.10

The ratios of steroid hormones on the apical and basolateral side calculated based on the values as described in the heatmap in Fig. 4. Abbreviations: AS; apical side, BS; basolateral side

Ratios	Monocultured BeWo b30		Monocultured HUVEC		Co-culture	
	AS/BS	BS/AS	AS/BS	BS/AS	AS/BS	BS/AS
Pregnenolone	20.7	0.05			4.0	0.25
Progesterone	6.4	0.2			1.8	0.5
Corticosterone			1.2	0.8	1.0	1.0
Cortisone	3.3	0.3	1.4	0.7	1.1	0.9
E1	0.5	2.0				
17 α E2	6.5	0.2			5.1	0.2
17 β E2	4.2	0.2			5.4	0.2

A.11: H2O2 oxidative stress

The ROS levels were measured after exposure to PS-MNPs in combination with a positive control H₂O₂ (Fig A.11). For all time points, exposure to 0.3 % H₂O₂ resulted in a significant increase in ROS levels.

Figure A.10. Oxidative stress measured in the co-culture. A DCFA-DA assay was used to determine the production of ROS after exposure to PS-MNPs. The second positive control that was included was 0.3 % H₂O₂. The bars represent the means \pm SD of three individual experiments in triplicate. The control was set as 1. Statistical analysis was performed with Student's t-test (** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$)

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.reprotox.2025.108956](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2025.108956).

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